

Preliminary Literature Review on Recent Research in Blast Performance of Tunnel Structures

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1. Introduction

Tunnel systems are particularly susceptible to explosives, in large part because the peak pressure and the impulse associated with the blast are extremely high and amplified by the confining structure, through reflection at the tunnel boundary (Choi 2009). Explosions in tunnels are generated from accidental and intentional attacks and range from small to large improvised explosive devices. Choi (2009) provides a detailed introduction to the topic, discussing the importance of understanding underground explosions and general explosion phenomenology, describing how explosions occur and the behavior of structures during the dynamic loading. The NCHRP (2006) issued a detailed report on underground facilities, covering a range of hazards and threats to tunnel elements and systems, including blast. This report provides a number of case studies on the vulnerability of tunnel elements. The FHWA (2013) issued high-level recommendations for tunnel security and AASHTO (2017) has provided some design requirements for blast in tunnels.

This report reviews a sample of blast-related tunnel literature, spanning a variety of geometrical tunnel layouts and explosion scenarios, including surface charges, internal, and external explosions. The section following this introduction summarizes the testing and analytical approaches employed by the reviewed literature. The next section provides summaries of the

reviewed literature. The studies are divided into those that focus on particular aspects of tunnel behavior and those that aim to develop design approaches. Concluding remarks, including future research needs, are then be provided.

This report was completed as a semester-long independent study project. Because of the limited time and the challenge inherent in understanding blast-related phenomena, the report is not intended to be comprehensive.

2. Testing and Analysis Procedures

Because full-scale experimental tests are very costly and risky, scaled models are often used to study the response of tunnel structures under blast loadings (Koneshwaran 2013). Such scaled-down experimental models commonly consist of centrifuge and shock tube testing. Centrifuge testing is useful for studying the response of buried structures to surface blast effects. Shock tube tests are useful for subjecting small tunnel liner and similar components to high-pressure blast loading in a controlled environment (Colombo 2016).

Numerical approaches are classified based on the fidelity of the model, ranging from simplified, through intermediate, to high fidelity. This is not a formal classification and authors differ in their usage of these terms. Simplified models are generally implemented as one- or two-dimensional models with simplified assumptions, often based on single-degree-of-freedom methods (Alostaz 2016). Intermediate models yield results comparable to those from high fidelity models for a fraction of the computation time. Although more efficient, these intermediate models generally result in conservative results due to the assumptions made when computing the blast-induced damage. High fidelity models cover a range of nonlinear problem in solids, fluids, and explosions. Koneshwaran et al. (2015) describe three numerical techniques available in LS-DYNA: Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE), smooth particle hydrodynamics (SPH), and Fluid-structural Interaction (FSI). These numerical techniques discretize the system in both time and space. The ALE is a coupling of pure Lagrangian and pure Eulerian modeling techniques. The pure Lagrangian method is suitable for solid objects, as the elements move with the mesh during deformation, while the pure Eulerian method is suitable for fluid objects, as the elements remain undeformed while materials flows from one element to another. As ALE combines the features of Lagrangian and Eulerian, their limitations are eliminated, however, there is an increase in computational time. The SPH is a meshless method that requires explicit nodal connectivity. The nodes behave similar to Lagrangian methods, as the nodes are allowed to move about the domain.

The interactions between these nodes are used to reproduce the hydrodynamic behavior. The FSI method is a coupling between ALE and Lagrangian methods. The surrounding air and explosive are modeled by ALE meshes, while the deformation of the structural parts uses Lagrangian meshes. The numerical programs used by studies reviewed in this report are LS-DYNA, ANSYS/CFX, ABAQUS/Explicit, AUTODYN, and ELFEN.

3. Literature Review

Although each of these studies had its own objectives, for the purpose of this literature review, they are placed in one of two categories. The first group of papers is devoted to examining particular details of tunnel response, while the other group is devoted primarily to producing design-oriented results. In the latter case, rapid design or simplified models are implemented to generate charts, graphs, and guidelines.

3.1. Aspects of Tunnel Response

Colombo and Martinelli (2014) studied the response of high-performance tunnel linings to blast-induced excitation. The tunnel consisted of a circular cross-section with an internal explosion located at the center of the tunnel structure. Two scenarios were considered. The first scenario investigated the response of high-performance fiber reinforced cementitious composite (HPFRCC) panels applied to new or existing tunnels. The second scenario investigated the response of a tunnel portion with incomplete mortar filling between the lining and the surface. Representative of poor grouting practices, this amplifies the internal forces suffered by the tunnel liner. Specimens were tested in a shock tube and linear elastic FE analysis was conducted to verify the response of the tunnel in the elastic domain. The finite element program ABAQUS/Explicit was used for all numerical simulations. HPFRCC panels were found to fail for blast pressures of 0.3 MPa with anchor spans of about 40 cm. The behavior of layered segments was found to survive up to about 1m of unfilled mortar zones and blast pressures in the order of 1 MPa.

Feldgun et al. (2014) investigate the effect of an explosion in a rectangular tunnel on a neighboring buried structure. Five cases were examined with varied charge location and distances between the tunnel structure and the nearby buried structure. One case studied the tunnel without considering a nearby buried structure. Analytical and numerical modeling was conducted to analyze the behavior of the structures. The AUTODYN commercial software was used to model the blast loading acting on the surface of the tunnel lining. The results of the numerical modeling

were used to verify the analytical equations developed. The presence of a second tunnel was found to worsen the stress distribution along the rectangular tunnel. Unsurprisingly, the charge location was found to affect the vertical peak velocity significantly.

Shin et al. (2010) studied the effect of blast-induced vibrations on horse-shoe shaped tunnels in soft rock. The proposed test investigates the performance of the tunnel due to blast-induced vibration at eight different locations on the cross-section and with varying blast locations. Two-dimensional numerical modeling and results from full-scale field tests were used in this study. Maximum particle velocity of the tunnel, maximum displacement, and stress of the lining were found to increase with a decrease in standoff distance. It was shown that the vertical velocity reduces near the tunnel. Proposed blast protection zones are also established by the parametric studies conducted. The chart is proposed for specific conditions and can be used as a preliminary evaluation.

Koneshwaran et al. (2015) investigated the performance of a circular tunnel structure with a surface explosion, incorporating fluid-structure interaction in the analysis. The response of a tunnel in dry sand was studied first, followed by a tunnel in saturated sand. Both of these studies were evaluated using the numerical modeling program LS-DYNA. The numerical technique implemented to consider fluid-structure interaction Arbitrary Lagrange-Eulerian with Lagrangian coupling. The numerical model was verified by centrifuge tests conducted by other authors. The results indicate that the explosive scenario is more severe in saturated soil than in dry sand. This is correlated with the liquefaction in the soil as it increases the pore water pressure in saturated soils.

3.2. *Design-Oriented Studies*

Alostaz (2016) investigated the performance of a tunnel structure located within a geological formation or waterbody. The tunnel geometry consisted of a circular cross-section with varying charge locations in and around the surrounding tunnel. Three scenarios were implemented in LS-DYNA to assess the performance of the structure, with the charge located in the interior of a tunnel, the exterior of the tunnel, and at the surface above the tunnel structure. A risk-based methodology was then proposed for selecting appropriate blast mitigations strategies. The methodology is a function of threat consequences, importance, and vulnerability of the structure. Importance and vulnerability are factors that can be determined by communication with the stakeholders, while consequences required engineering analyses to determine the amount of potential damage to a

threat. Measures were provided to reduce the likelihood of large-scale damage, catastrophic failure, or hazardous conditions of the tunnel.

Mitelman and Elmo (2015) studied rock spalling for the purposes of tunnel support design to withstand blast loading. The tunnel geometry consists of a circular cross-section with an external explosion. One- and two-dimensional numerical modeling was conducted to compare with analytical spalling equations and field test results. The numerical program ELFEN was used to test scenarios with varying tensile strengths. The authors produced a flowchart to assist the engineer in selecting a support system to guard against rock spalling. The flowchart uses a toolbox approach to model liner response to rock mass damage induced by blast loading. This approach would allow support design of tunnels to account for blast-induced damage by following the procedures listed on the flowchart.

Bai et al. (2018) investigated the vulnerability of road tunnels with reinforced concrete liners subjected to internal explosions. The tunnel geometries consisted of rectangular, circular, and horseshoe cross sections. This study proposed a framework for blast damage assessment using intermediate complexity analysis aimed at producing accurate, conservative assessments of blast-induced damage at a fraction of the computational effort of high-fidelity models. The analytical equations were implemented in a CAD environment and Matlab to generate breach and spall damage. This approach was then found to be in good agreement with LS-DYNA results. The simplified model allows engineers to produce a quick and conservative estimate of the damage to the tunnel for charge sizes of various intensities.

4. Recommendations for Future Research

This section summarizes the future research needs identified in the studies that were reviewed. Feldgun et al. (2014) mentioned that experimental results on the effect of an explosion in a tunnel on a neighboring tunnel would help them verify their results. Mitelman et al. (2015) called for 3D analysis work that would account for the lateral resistance of the tunnel liner and additional supports systems such as bolts and mesh reinforced concrete or steel sets embedded in concrete. This would allow for a better understanding of the spalling behavior in a tunnel lining. Choi (2009) requested real-scale tunnel explosion test to validate numerical predictions. Another request was to conduct field-test of various tunnel blast protection measures to grasp a better understanding of the protection measures. Koneshwaran et al. (2015) called for full-scale field experiments that study the response of tunnels under surface blast loadings. Bai et al. (2017) mention that future

efforts of theirs will emphasize improvement of analytical approaches to increase accuracy and provide efficient predictions. They are also interested in the coupled effect of blast and fire. NCHRP (2006) lists several topics for potential research including the evaluation of the effects of fire on the tunnel structure, development of ground improvement retrofitting schemes, construction of test tunnels or models, and identifying retrofit technologies to enhance safety.

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